

**FOOD AND FEEDING HABITS OF *CYPRINUS CARPIO* FROM MIRANI DAM,
DISTRICT TURBAT, BALOCHISTAN PAKISTAN**

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Abstract

Based on its nutrition and eating habits, the Cyprinus carpio fish is a bottom feeder, a euryphage, as well as a carni-omnivore. Samples of this Fish were taken monthly from Mirani Dam in Turbat, Balochistani between January and December of 2022. A total of 225 samples were obtained for this inquiry. These fish had progressively an empty gut score of 40 (14.28%), followed by quarters of 50 (17.85%), half of 80 (28.59%), third quarter of 65 (23.21%), and a complete gut score of 45 (16.07%). Further research revealed that the gut fulness was higher on a monthly basis in November (92), October (90), September (88), August (85), June (81) and July (80). Lower levels were recorded in February (60), March (63), April (70), January (70), May (75), and December (77). The bulk of the stomach contents were composed of debris (20.41), insects (15.93), hemiptera (13.42), plecoptra (10.26), coleopotera (8.43), phytoplankton (5.72), crustaceans (5.16), zooplankton (4.22), sand (3.81), higher plants (3.39), algae (2.45), and aquatic weeds (2.45). (1.98).

KEYWORDS: Cyprinus carpio, nutrition, Aquatic weeds, Zooplankton, Miscellaneous
INTRODUCTION

Cyprinus carpio, is a bony fish that belongs to the class Osteichthyes and being a member of the family Cyprinidae and the order Cypriniformes which is one of its significant groups, and it may be found worldwide in many bodies of water, such as streams, pools, rivers, and lakes (Manon & Hossain, 2011). *Cyprinus carpio* was introduced to Pakistani waters in 1964 from Thailand (Mondol et al., 2013). Gulfam is locally referred to *Cyprinus carpio*. Mirani dam is a habitat to a significant population of *Cyprinus carpio*.

The first artificial fish which was successfully kept into the waters worldwide by humans was the common carp (Mangi & Memon, 2017). Common carp was imported by

Romans from the Danubi River and exported to Europe (Jha & Barat, 2005). It is considered to be the most widely cultured fish species globally (Kloskowski, 2011). It is found in lakes, reservoirs, and other bodies of moving water. It has been introduced to the waters of Asia and Europe (Rahman et al., 2006). *Cyprinus carpio* can maintain its body in a variety of environmental conditions due to its great tolerance (Civera-Cerecedo et al., 2004). Regardless of the fact that it can withstand temperatures of up to 40 degrees and as low as 2 degrees, it thrives in water that is normally between 15 and 32 degrees Celsius (Saikia & Das, 2009). *Cyprinus carpio* is an omnivore that consumes grains, macrophytes, plankton, insects, nematodes, and crustaceans as food (Debnath et al., 2005). In regions where the carps have been imported, issues have been brought on about its feeding method of digging in the silt and extracting food from the clay (Anton-Pardo et al., 2014).

By removing buried plants, it makes the water colder. While foraging near the water's bottom, these fish are bothered by the sediment which can be harmful to local fauna (EL-Fiky, 2003). These feeder fish contain sand, mud, and other debris in their digestive tracts all the year round (Rahman & Meyer, 2009). The type and amount of natural food sources that are provided and ingested have a tremendous impact on a fish's ability to grow.

Consequently, certain differences have been found in the amount and the quality of food ingredients (Shafi et al., 2012). Numerous biotic and abiotic factors have an impact on the quantitative and qualitative variability of organic food products in an aquatic environment (Naik et al., 2015). Every month, various fish have distinct dietary behaviors. Seasonal changes in the species' makeup of the food-producing species are the cause of this variation and Fish has varying diets and dietary habits due to season, size of fish, many ecological conditions, and the types of food that are found in the body of water (Rahman et al., 2008).

Research Methodology

Research design

The following study is planned as a quantitative approach. To provide support for the latest plan's general approach and conduct more thorough investigations into the study's numerous components.

Study area

Mirani dam is located on Dasht River in district Kech (Turbat), Balochistan. Construction of Mirani dam started on July 8, 2002, and it was completed in July 2006. In November 2006, General Parvez Musharref, the then president of Pakistan, officially inaugurated it. It

is 35 feet in width, 3350 feet in length, and 127 feet in height. It can hold more than 300,000-million-acre feet of water. Numerous fish species, such as tilapia, Rahu, cow, and salmon fish, crocodiles, various amphibians, and a variety of predators, omnivores, and herbivores, as well as other animals, live in the dam.

Figure 1: Mirani Dam

Data collection

Two categories of data were utilized in the current study: primary data and secondary data. In the original data, 230 fish were collected, and the secondary data, which was in the form of review papers, books, scholarly articles, and journals, was carefully reviewed, helped identify the primary data.

Sampling method

Fishermen from the Mirani Dam collected 230 fish specimens over the course of the months of January 2021 to December 2021. To show eating and feeding, fish specimens were preserved in formalin solutions containing between 10 and 15 percent by volume. Five milliliters of formalin were injected into the stomachs of the specimens using syringes with a volume of ten milliliters to prevent enzyme activity. These fish sample were transferred in their frozen ice containers to the University of Baluchistan's Zoology Department in Quetta.

Figure 2: Samples of *Cyprinus carpio*

Research analysis tools

Fish identification;

Used the established procedures and guidelines for identifying fish samples by (Imran et al., 2021; Manon & Hossain, 2011)

Gut content analysis

Methodically dissected each fish, collected the stomach contents, and then submerged them in formalin (5–10%). investigated the gut's components under a microscope with ocular lens (Nikon Eclipse E200). Using the pictures created by several researchers, all of the species were identified (Hellowell & Abel, 1971; Hyslop, 1980). Comparable keys are also provided by (Edmondson et al., 1959)

Estimation of gut contents

estimating gut contents by the use of point volumetric (Pillay, 1952) and frequency of occurrence (Hynes, 1950) methods. Each dietary component in the intestine was given a distinct amount of points using a point volumetric approach based on volume. Point

$$\text{Volumetric Method} = \frac{\text{No of points allocated to component}}{\text{Total points allocated to sub-sample}} \times 100$$

Each sample's meal components are evaluated after which the stomach contents are estimated and kept. The number of guts in which food items were discovered was counted. Each food item was then observed, and its proportion to the total number of guts was expressed, describing the frequency of occurrences (Hynes, 1950).

$$P = \frac{b}{a} \times 100$$

a = Total of the fishes observed with food in their guts,

b = the number of the fishes that possess a specific food ingredient, p = percentage of each food item's occurrences.

Gastro-somatic index

Gastro-somatic Index was calculated by identifying variations in eating intensity on a monthly basis and using the appropriate formulas used by (Mesoenyama, 2017; Nikiforov-Nikishin et al., 2022), as cited in (Achakzai et al., 2015)

$$\text{GaSI}(\%) = \frac{\text{weightofgut}(g)}{\text{weightoffish}(g)} \times 100$$

Gut fullness and its category

Used the gravimetric method to measure how full the stomach was (Hynes 1950)

$$\text{Gravimetric method} = \frac{\text{Totalgutcontentsweight}}{\text{TotalFishweight}} \times 100$$

The stomach content of the *Cyprinus carpio* samples were divided into five groups: full= (100%), empty= (0%) and quarter, half, and third quarter, each comprising (25 %), (50 %) (75 %) of the total.

Index of preponderance

Index Of predominance provides reliable information regarding classification of different food components investigated the relative importance of gut contents, as well as frequency of occurrence and varied food components volume. Used a formula to obtain the index of predominance by Natarjan and jhingran (1961) (Mohan & Sankaran, 1988)

$$I = \frac{ViOi}{\sum ViOi} \times 100$$

Where:

I = index of Preponderance

vi= Volume Percentage

oi= Occurrence Percentage

\sum = Summation

Table 1. Grades of different gut-contents in *C. carpio* in Mirani dam district Turbat, Balochistan

S. No	Food items	% Composition of items by Volume (Vi)	Occurrence (Oi)	ViOi	Index of preponderance $I = \frac{ViOi}{\sum ViOi} \times 100$	Grade by Volume
1	Detritus	20.41	25.54	521.271	41.48	I
2	Insects	15.93	16.34	260.296	20.71	II
3	Hemiptera	13.42	12.6	169.092	13.45	III
4	Plecoptera	10.26	10.22	104.857	8.34	IV
5	Coleoptera	8.43	9.26	78.0618	6.05	V
6	Phytoplankton	5.72	7.34	41.9848	3.74	VI
7	Crustacean	5.16	5.45	28.122	2.23	VII
8	Zooplankton	4.82	4.22	20.3404	1.5	VIII
9	Sand	4.22	3.13	13.2086	1.05	IX
10	Miscellaneous	3.81	2.23	8.4963	0.67	X
11	Higher Plant	3.39	2.11	7.1529	0.5	XI
12	Algae	2.45	1.33	3.2585	0.25	XII
13	Aquatic weeds	1.98	0.23	0.4554	0.03	XIII

Figure 1: Food items of *C. Carpio* in Mirani dam

Gut fullness and Gastrostatic Index (GaSI)

The differences were found in the GaSI and stomach fullness in the month of November (192), October (90), September (88), August (85), June (81) and July (82) advanced stomach fullness was noted (80). The months of February (60), March (63), April (70), January (70), May (75), and December had lower readings (77). Table 2.

Figure 2: Gut fullness of *C. Carpio* of Mirani dam district Turbat

Table 2: Monthly gut-fullness and gastro-index (GaSI) in *C. Carpio* of Mirani dam district Turbat, Balochistan

Months	Gut fullness	GaSI
January	70	1.4
February	60	1.2
March	63	1.4
April	70	1.1
May	75	1.3
June	81	1.4
July	80	1.4
August	85	1.5
September	88	1.6
October	90	1.7
November	92	1.8
December	77	1.7
Average	78.75	1.46

Figure 3: Index of preponderance of *C. Carpio* in Mirani dam district Turbat Balochistan

Stomach Categories

During the research period 225 fishes' stomach were studied, with big differences in the categories e.g: 40 (14.28%) = empty, 50 (17.85) = quarter, 80 (28.59%) = half, 65 (23.21%) = three quarter and 45 (16.07%) = full.

Table 3: Stomachs of *C. Carpio* of Mirani dam district Turbat Balochistan

State	No of guts	Percentage
Empty	40	14.28
Quarter	50	17.85
Half	80	28.59
Three Quarter	65	23.21
Full	45	16.07
Total	225	100

Figure 4: Gut fullness of *C. Carpio* in Mirani dam district Turbat Balochistan

DISCUSSION RECOMMENDATIONS

The investigation was on the food habit and analysis of gut composition of *Cyprinus carpio* from Mirani dam in Turbat. It has been determined that *Cyprinus carpio* is an omnivore fish. Since *Cyprinus carpio* is a widely distributed and commercially significant fish in Pakistan, researchers can readily locate and conduct study on it. In order to ensure optimal management, the following suggestions are made based on the research done on the species' dietary and feeding behaviors.

The capturing of undersized fish by illegal fishers has been documented. If adequate protective measures are not strengthened, this will cause the stock to fall.

The current work may not be adequate to offer a comprehensive picture of the feeding habits of *Cyprinus carpio*, thus more research is required to comprehend the interactions of the fish with other species and its food selectivity on temporal and geographical dimensions.

The ecological balance of the Mirani dam is sufficient for detritus, benthic creatures, and macrophytes, which were common food sources for *Cyprinus*, as the current study demonstrated.

If there are environmental issues, there was no doubt a feeding issue for the species. Therefore, it is important to maintain the dam's ecological balance in a reasonable way.

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